

Practice- or results-based subsidies: balancing the direct costs for soil carbon sequestration and transaction costs for farmers and monitoring agencies

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Policymakers increasingly seek to promote agricultural carbon sequestration, avoiding both income losses for farmers and excessive public implementation costs. This study compares practice- and results-based subsidies to soil carbon sequestration with respect to their total costs, sequestration achieved, and income effects. We develop a numerical model that maximizes social net benefits while accounting for private transaction costs, public monitoring costs, and regional and farm type heterogeneity. The findings reveal that results-based subsidies deliver higher net benefits and sequestration. The per hectare monitoring costs for a practice-based scheme must be less than 30 percent of those for a results-based scheme for the former to deliver higher net benefits, given a carbon price of 250 €/tCO_{2e}. Sensitivity analysis shows that higher carbon prices require the monitoring costs of a practice-based scheme to be even lower relative to those of a results-based scheme in order to outperform it.

Keywords: Agriculture, Agri-environmental Support, Carbon Sequestration, Monitoring Costs, Practice- and Results-based Subsidies

JEL Codes: Q54, Q24, Q58, H52

outcomes. Results-based support is often argued by economists to improve cost-effectiveness by directing support to the most productive sites in terms of sequestration output (Abler 2008; Bamière et al. 2021; Hasler et al. 2022; Parks and Hardie 1995; Pautsch et al. 2001). However, they may require field-based MRV of carbon changes, and therefore frequently entail higher costs than practice-based alternatives (Richards 2000; Cacho et al. 2004). This raises the question of whether results-based subsidies for carbon sequestration that require in-field monitoring yield higher net benefits than uniform per-hectare payments, once all costs are taken into consideration.

Most agri-environmental support currently provided in the EU countries is delivered through voluntary practice-based schemes (European Commission 2024a; Hasler et al. 2022). Although very few programs explicitly target carbon sequestration, several remunerate for practices that indirectly promote it, such as the Danish payments for extending grassland areas and cultivating cover crops (European Commission 2021; Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries in Denmark, 2023; Ministry of the Environment and Food in Denmark/EPA 2017). A couple of recently developed pilot schemes have adopted results-based approaches for carbon sequestration, such as the Austrian Humus-Program, where farmers voluntarily agree to provide sequestration by implementing measures that build up soil organic matter, while earning 30 € per reported additional tonne of stored CO₂e³. Similarly, the French Label Bas Carbone certify emission reductions or sequestration, which can subsequently be marketed as carbon credits on voluntary markets, with 494 projects certified in 2023 (Ministère de la transition énergétique 2024). These examples indicate a potentially growing interest in results-based incentives for carbon sequestration, which allow farmers to choose the most efficient

³ The program is managed locally and targets a smaller group of farmers, with around 300 participants across Austria. The payments are funded by companies looking to offset their unavoidable carbon emissions (Verein Ökoregion Kaindorf 2024).

combination of measures at each site, hence directing sequestration efforts to locations and activities that provide the largest amount of sequestration for least cost (Antle et al. 2003; Richards 2004).

Despite their appeal, results-based schemes face practical obstacles, which might explain the widespread use of practice-based instruments in an EU context. Farmer heterogeneity and the large number of farmers potentially involved tend to increase public transaction costs for implementation of results-based policies (Bartkowski et al. 2021; McCann 2013; Gren 2004). These costs, including MRV costs, directly influence the cost-effectiveness of schemes (Mettepenningen and Van Huylenbroeck 2009). In particular, MRV costs can be substantial when there is high heterogeneity in environmental and farm conditions, because of increased sampling requirements (Cacho et al. 2004). In contrast, practice-based payments are based on pre-defined and often easily visible actions and are therefore easier to monitor (Keenleyside 2015), especially in open space areas (Vatn 2002). Consequently, monitoring carbon sequestration may entail such high administrative costs that results-based schemes could be more costly per unit of sequestered carbon compared to uniform area schemes (Stavins 1999).

Several empirical studies have examined whether increased targeting of results is better to encourage carbon sequestration provision or agricultural emissions reductions (Antle et al. 2003; Bamière et al. 2021; Parks and Hardie 1995; Pautsch et al. 2001; Tarruella et al. 2025,). Parks and Hardie (1995), using a simulation-based cost-minimization model of land enrollment decisions, investigate enrollment in US government programs for converting agricultural land to forests. They show that selecting land based on the cost per ton of carbon sequestered achieves greater sequestration than selection based on rental cost per acre, although it leads to less land being enrolled. Pautsch et al. (2001), applying a simulation model combining ecological and economic components to derive abatement cost curves, find that differentiating tillage payments by sequestration lowers average abatement costs per unit of sequestered

carbon relative to uniform per-hectare support. Bamière et al. (2021) reach similar conclusions in a French context using a bio-economic optimization model calibrated to French agriculture that demonstrates that results-based payments for no-till, extension of temporary grasslands, and hedge planting are more cost-effective than command-and-control regulation for the same practices, with the results-based instrument leading to higher decreases in net emission. Taruella et al. (2025) develops an optimization algorithm to compare the efficacy of different targeting approaches for agricultural emissions reductions. Contrasting with the previously mentioned studies it finds that when heterogeneous abatement costs are introduced, less targeted support might be more cost-effective than farm-level targets, when both consider abatement cost heterogeneity. None of the studies mentioned consider the difference in public transaction costs associated with the use of practice- and results-based policy instruments. We only found a single study, Antle et al. (2003), that incorporates transaction costs in terms of public MRV costs, by developing and applying an integrated assessment framework that explicitly models the efficiency of alternative soil-carbon contracts by accounting for spatial heterogeneity in agricultural systems. The authors find that results-based instruments provide higher overall gains despite additional MRV expenses. However, the study adds MRV costs *ex post*, i.e., the potential impact of these costs on optimal carbon sequestration and on the distribution of sequestration and costs across farms is not taken into account. Hence, there is reason to ask how policy instrument choices are affected when public MRV costs are treated as an endogenous part of the optimization problem. This study aims to address that knowledge gap.

We develop a numerical model of the policymaker's decision problem that maximizes the net social benefits of sequestration while accounting for differences in public monitoring costs across policy instruments and farms. The model is applied to Danish agriculture using empirical data and accounting for heterogeneity in soil organic carbon sequestration potential

seeding⁴ and/or minimal mechanical soil disturbance through non-turning soil cultivation (Rosa-Schleich et al. 2019). When farmers adopt reduced tillage, carbon losses are reduced in topsoil because tillage and plowing are associated with soil organic carbon (SOC) decomposition and erosion. Lastly, the conversion of arable land into grassland prevents carbon release from soil. That is because, compared to arable land, the soils of grasslands are characterized by high soil carbon stocks (Gocht et al. 2016), due to highly developed root systems and large belowground biomass (Norderhaug et al. 2023). The carbon sequestered by measure j applied in a landholding is assumed to be a function of the area allocated to the measure, i.e. $X_{ij}(A_{ij})$, with $X_{ij}(A_{ij})$ differentiable and strictly increasing in A_{ij} .⁵ Notably, we focus on soil organic carbon sequestration only. That is, we model changes in soil organic carbon induced by alternative management practices, while disregarding changes in biomass and emissions.

We introduce equation (1) to represent the landholding's capacity restrictions with respect to the area allocated to measure j , where \bar{A}_{ij} is the total area available for implementation of a measure:

$$(1) A_{ij} \leq \bar{A}_{ij}.$$

We assume that grassland cannot be implemented on the same land as either of the other two measures, while cover crops and reduced tillage may be implemented on the same land as shown by Canales et al. (2020). This is expressed as follows:

$$(2) A_{i\text{ grass}} + A_{i\text{ till}} \leq \bar{A}_i$$

and

$$(3) A_{i\text{ grass}} + A_{i\text{ cc}} \leq \bar{A}_i.$$

⁴ When seeds are planted directly into the soil using specialized equipment, thereby reducing the need for tillage.

⁵ This implies that an inverse $A_{ij} = A_{ij}^{-1}(X_{ij})$ exists.

where the parameter \bar{A}_i represents the cropland area of the landholding.

When land is allocated for carbon sequestration, farmers⁶ face adoption costs. We consider two types of adoption costs, $C_{ij}^m(A_{ij})$ and $C_{ij}^t(X_{ij})$, with the superscripts m and t indicating direct mitigation and private transaction costs, respectively. Direct mitigation costs are foregone profits, and capital, operation, maintenance, and management expenses of producing environmental services that accrue to farmers. We assume that these costs are convex and increasing in the area dedicated to measure j . Private transaction costs are the farmers' incremental costs for engaging in sequestration (Joas and Flachslund 2016; Krutilla and Krause 2011), i.e. all costs in addition to direct mitigation costs incurred by the farmer. This includes, e.g., the opportunity cost of time spent completing forms, researching sequestration measures, planning their implementation, voluntarily registering in government programs, communicating with relevant authorities, and the costs of hiring advisory services. Such costs can vary with farmer characteristics and the complexity, uncertainty and time requirements of the administration itself (Vernimmen et al. 2000). Following Joas and Flachslund (2016) Phan et al. (2017) and Karpavicius et al. (2026), we assume that private transaction costs are a convex and increasing function of sequestration, X_{ij} . The assumed convexity of adoption costs ensures a well-behaved optimization problem, thus supporting an interior solution. Although transaction costs may include fixed components unrelated to the amount of land enrolled or environmental output, empirical studies do not find evidence of economies of scale in sequestration transaction costs (Phan et al., 2017; Karpavicius et al., 2026). Combined with analytical convenience, this motivates our assumption of a convex transaction cost function.⁷

⁶ In this study, we use the term “farmer” to refer to the actor who operates and manages a landholding and is eligible for applying for agricultural support schemes at that landholding, which may or may not be the landowner.

⁷ The impact of changes in convexity assumptions for transaction costs on the optimal sequestration supply is not considered in this study, but the interested reader may refer to Karpavicius et al. (2025) for an application with Danish agricultural data.

In addition to farmers' adoption costs, there are public transaction costs $C_{ij}^g(A_{ij})$, associated with the governmental scheme that incentivizes sequestration provision. While this could entail a wider variety of cost types, we focus on MRV costs. We assume that formal MRV activities are carried out and financed by the regulator, while any farmer compliance effort is captured within the previously mentioned private transaction costs. We assume that these MRV costs accrue due to field assessments to monitor either the carbon output or area allocation, depending on the policy instrument design⁸. This is motivated by soil sampling being the most reliable method for measuring carbon sequestration (Block et al. 2024), and by field visits being the standard procedure to ensure compliance with agri-environmental schemes (European Commission 2024a). There could be alternative options for control of compliance, e.g. models could be used to predict environmental outcomes under results-based scheme, but these models still require data for their calibration (Bartkowski et al. 2021). In principle, such data could be gathered using non-field based technologies like remote sensing, but this may not be sufficient to ascertain contributions at a high level of precision (Stanley 2024) and a choice experiment applied in Spain suggests that farmers have limited confidence in the use of remote sensing technology, therefore requiring significantly higher remuneration if such an approach is applied (Villanueva et al. 2024). Further, Karpavicius et al.(2026) finds no significant difference in MRV costs for carbon sequestration projects that use remote sensing, relative to those using field assessments. Given this evidence, we choose not to include model-based monitoring in the present study. Based on studies showing a positive relationship between MRV costs and the area to be monitored (Cacho et al. 2004; Karpavicius et al., 2026; Zaks and Kucharik 2011) we assume that MRV costs increase linearly with A_{ij} .

⁸ We assume some kind of on-site measurement is necessary regardless of the policy instrument design.

Finally, we assume the sequestered carbon will yield a societal benefit, with the parameter b indicating the constant marginal benefit of a tonne of unit carbon removal. The benefits of carbon sequestration from measure j , $B_{ij}(X_{ij}(A_{ij}))$, are defined as:

$$(4) B_{ij}(X_{ij}(A_{ij})) = b \cdot X_{ij}(A_{ij}).$$

2.1. Social optimum

We analyze the problem of an environmental regulator that chooses the areas A_{ij} to maximize the net benefits, NB , given by the problem below:

$$(5) \text{Max}_{A_{ij}} NB = \sum_j \sum_{i=1}^n [B_{ij}(X_{ij}(A_{ij})) - C_{ij}^m(A_{ij}) - C_{ij}^t(X_{ij}(A_{ij})) - C_{ij}^g(A_{ij})]$$

s. t.

(1) – (3).

$-A_{ij} \leq 0,$

$\forall i, j.$

The net benefits are defined as the sum of societal benefits from carbon sequestration minus farmers' adoption and public MRV costs, subject to the area restrictions and the non-negativity condition for A_{ij} .

The Lagrangian function for the above optimization problem is:

$$(6) L = \sum_j \sum_{i=1}^n [B_{ij}(X_{ij}(A_{ij})) - C_{ij}^m(A_{ij}) - C_{ij}^t(X_{ij}(A_{ij})) - C_{ij}^g(A_{ij}) - \lambda_{ij}(A_{ij} - \bar{A}_{ij}) - \mu_{i1}(A_{i \text{ grass}} + A_{i \text{ cc}} - \bar{A}_i) - \mu_{i2}(A_{i \text{ grass}} + A_{i \text{ till}} - \bar{A}_i)],$$

where the term λ_{ij} is the Lagrange multiplier for each measure's capacity constraint, and the terms μ_{i1} and μ_{i2} are Lagrange multipliers for the joint area constraints. The Karush-Kuhn-Tucker (KKT) conditions necessary for optimality include:

$$(7) \frac{\partial L}{\partial A_{i \text{ cc}}} = b \frac{\partial X_{i \text{ cc}}}{\partial A_{i \text{ cc}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ cc}}^m}{\partial A_{i \text{ cc}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ cc}}^t}{\partial X_{i \text{ cc}}} \frac{\partial X_{i \text{ cc}}}{\partial A_{i \text{ cc}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ cc}}^g}{\partial A_{i \text{ cc}}} - \lambda_{i \text{ cc}} - \mu_{i1} = 0,$$

$$(8) \frac{\partial L}{\partial A_{i \text{ grass}}} = b \frac{\partial X_{i \text{ grass}}}{\partial A_{i \text{ grass}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ grass}}^m}{\partial A_{i \text{ grass}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ grass}}^t}{\partial X_{i \text{ grass}}} \frac{\partial X_{i \text{ grass}}}{\partial A_{i \text{ grass}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ grass}}^g}{\partial A_{i \text{ grass}}} - \lambda_{i \text{ grass}} - \mu_{i1} - \mu_{i2} = 0 \text{ and}$$

$$(9) \frac{\partial L}{\partial A_{i \text{ till}}} = b \frac{\partial X_{i \text{ till}}}{\partial A_{i \text{ till}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ till}}^m}{\partial A_{i \text{ till}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ till}}^t}{\partial X_{i \text{ till}}} \frac{\partial X_{i \text{ till}}}{\partial A_{i \text{ till}}} - \frac{\partial C_{i \text{ till}}^g}{\partial A_{i \text{ till}}} - \lambda_{i \text{ till}} - \mu_{i2} = 0,$$

with the associated slackness conditions:

$$(10) \quad \lambda_{ij}(A_{ij} - \bar{A}_{ij}) = 0,$$

$$(11) \quad \mu_{i1}(A_{i \text{ grass}} + A_{i \text{ cc}} - \bar{A}_i) = 0,$$

$$(12) \quad \mu_{i2}(A_{i \text{ grass}} + A_{i \text{ till}} - \bar{A}_i) = 0.$$

Equation (7)-(9) shows that the marginal gross benefits of enrolling an additional hectare in measure j , $b \cdot \partial X_{ij} / \partial A_{ij}$, should be equal to the sum of the marginal mitigation cost, $\partial C_{ij}^m / \partial A_{ij}$, and the marginal private and public transaction costs, $(\partial C_{ij}^t / \partial X_{ij}) \cdot (\partial X_{ij} / \partial A_{ij})$ and $\partial C_{ij}^g / \partial A_{ij}$, respectively, and the sum of the shadow values on the respective land constraints. Thus, the optimal area allocated for a measure will depend on the MRV costs. Therefore, when practice- and results-based instruments have distinct MRV costs, the choice of policy instrument affects the optimal level of carbon sequestration.

Using the first-order conditions from the decision problem and the Lagrangian above, the policy maker could implement a differentiated per-hectare subsidy that induces farmers to choose the socially optimal land allocation. Assuming an interior solution, the optimal Pigouvian (first-best) differentiated per-hectare subsidy s_{ij}^{INP} is defined by:

$$(13) \quad s_{ij}^{INP} = b \frac{\partial X_{ij}}{\partial A_{ij}} - \frac{\partial C_{ij}^g}{\partial A_{ij}}.$$

The terms $\partial X_{ij} / \partial A_{ij}$ and $\partial C_{ij}^g / \partial A_{ij}$ in equation (13) indicate that the optimal per hectare payment varies across landholdings and measures. Landholdings that sequester more carbon per hectare when using measure j receive higher per hectare payments for that measure. Also, landholdings for which the marginal public MRV costs are low receive higher payments.

Equation (13) could be reformulated to inform on the equivalent optimal Pigouvian subsidy per tonne of CO₂e of carbon sequestered, s_{ij}^{OUT} . Diving through by $\frac{\partial X_{ij}}{\partial A_{ij}}$ we obtain s_{ij}^{OUT} as:

$$(14) \quad s_{ij}^{OUT} = s_{ij}^{INP} / \frac{\partial X_{ij}}{\partial A_{ij}} = b - \frac{\partial C_{ij}^g}{\partial A_{ij}} / \frac{\partial X_{ij}}{\partial A_{ij}}.$$

Then, using the inverse of $X_{ij}(A_{ij})$, $A_{ij} = A_{ij}^{-1}(X_{ij})$, public MRV costs, $C_{ij}^g(A_{ij})$, can be expressed as a function of the sequestration output X_{ij} , and equation (14) simplifies to:

$$(15) \quad s_{ij}^{OUT} = b - \frac{\partial C_{ij}^g}{\partial X_{ij}}$$

If offered to farmers, the subsidy in equation (15) will ensure that they choose to enroll an optimal amount of land into the scheme, equal to that defined by equations (7)–(9). Thus, the optimal Pigouvian payment per tonne of carbon in equation (15) equals the marginal social value of soil organic carbon sequestration b net of the government's marginal MRV cost per additional tonne sequestered, where the latter increases with the expansion of enrolled area. The Pigouvian subsidy, therefore, is differentiated by i and j , therefore constituting a results-based payment.

Due to the high level of differentiation, the first-best practice-based instrument in equation (13) would require substantial administrative efforts, similar to that for the first best results-based subsidy in equation (15). The standard arguments for the use of a practice-based instrument, i.e. lower MRV requirements compared to a results-based instrument, would therefore not hold. In the following, we therefore only consider the first-best results-based subsidy defined in equation (15) and compare it to a uniform practice-based described in the following section.

2.2. Uniform payments for carbon sequestration

Next, we examine the case where the environmental regulator introduces a second-best policy instrument, a uniform per-hectare subsidy for each measure. The motivation for considering

uniform subsidies arises from its practical implementation advantages, while it also aligns with existing payments in agri-environmental schemes. Compared to the first-best practice-based subsidy described in the previous section, the uniform practice-based subsidy has fewer information requirements, because it will not be differentiated based on landholdings' per hectare sequestration or MRV costs.

We formulate the regulator's objective as one of choosing an optimal uniform practice-based subsidy for each measure, s_j^{UNI} , that maximizes net benefits (*NB*) of public spending. We model the problem as a two-level Stackelberg game, assuming the government anticipates that farmers will respond to the subsidy by enrolling land up to the point where their marginal revenue equals the marginal cost.

Using backwards induction and, hence, starting with the farmers' problem we assume that farmers maximize their net revenues, NR_i , of engaging in carbon sequestration as expressed by equation (16) below.

$$(16) \quad \text{Max}_{A_{ij}} NR_i = \sum_j [s_j^{UNI} A_{ij} - C_{ij}^m(A_{ij}) - C_{ij}^t(X_{ij}(A_{ij}))] \quad s. t.$$

$$(1) - (3).$$

$$-A_{ij} \leq 0,$$

$$\forall j.$$

Here, $s_j^{UNI} A_{ij}$ represents the gross revenue of engaging in carbon sequestration measure j .

The net revenue is found by subtracting adoption costs, $C_{ij}^m(A_{ij}) + C_{ij}^t(X_{ij})$. As before, the maximization is subjected to the area and non-negativity restrictions for A_{ij} .

The Lagrangian function for Equation (16) can be expressed as:

$$(17) \quad L = \sum_j s_j^{UNI} A_{ij} - C_{ij}^m(A_{ij}) - C_{ij}^t(X_{ij}(A_{ij})) - \lambda_{ij}(A_{ij} - \bar{A}_{ij}) - \mu_{i1}(A_{i\text{grass}} + A_{i\text{cc}} - \bar{A}_t) - \mu_{i2}(A_{i\text{grass}} + A_{i\text{till}} - \bar{A}_t).$$

The FOCs for this problem are found as:

$$(18) \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial A_{i\,cc}} = S_{cc}^{UNI} - \frac{\partial C_{i\,cc}^m}{\partial A_{i\,cc}} - \left(\frac{\partial C_{i\,cc}^t}{\partial X_{i\,cc}} \frac{\partial X_{i\,cc}}{\partial A_{i\,cc}} \right) - \lambda_{i\,cc} - \mu_{i1} = 0$$

$$(19) \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial A_{i\,grass}} = S_{grass}^{UNI} - \frac{\partial C_{i\,grass}^m}{\partial A_{i\,grass}} - \left(\frac{\partial C_{i\,grass}^t}{\partial X_{i\,grass}} \frac{\partial X_{i\,grass}}{\partial A_{i\,grass}} \right) - \lambda_{i\,grass} - \mu_{i1} - \mu_{i2} = 0$$

$$(20) \quad \frac{\partial L}{\partial A_{i\,till}} = S_{till}^{UNI} - \frac{\partial C_{i\,till}^m}{\partial A_{i\,till}} - \left(\frac{\partial C_{i\,till}^t}{\partial X_{i\,till}} \frac{\partial X_{i\,till}}{\partial A_{i\,till}} \right) - \lambda_{i\,till} - \mu_{i2} = 0$$

Equations (18)-(20) imply that the privately optimal land allocation, A_{ij}^* , requires that the uniform subsidy equals the sum of marginal adoption costs, and the shadow value of land use constraints. From equations (18)-(20), we describe the farmer's response function $A_{ij}^*(s_j^{UNI})$:

$$(21) \quad A_{ij}^*(s_j^{UNI}) = \operatorname{argmax} NR_i(A_{ij}, s_j^{UNI}).$$

Next, we turn to the regulator's decision problem of choosing the uniform subsidy s_j^{UNI} that maximizes net benefits of public funding for carbon sequestration, i.e., maximizes the gross benefits from sequestration minus the subsidy costs and public transaction costs. The regulator's problem is thus formulated as:

$$(22) \quad \operatorname{Max}_{s_j^{UNI}} NB = \sum_j \sum_{i=1}^n \left[bX_{ij} \left(A_{ij}^*(s_j^{UNI}) \right) - s_j A_{ij}^*(s_j^{UNI}) - C_{ij}^g \left(A_{ij}^*(s_j^{UNI}) \right) \right]$$

s. t.

$$A_{ij}^*(s_j^{UNI}) = \operatorname{argmax} NR_i(A_{ij}, s_j^{UNI}).$$

$\forall i, j.$

To solve for the optimal subsidy s_j^{UNI} , we substitute $A_{ij} = A_{ij}^*(s_j^{UNI})$, with $\partial A_{ij} / \partial s_j^{UNI} > 0$, and take the FOC:

$$(23) \quad \frac{\partial NB}{\partial s_j^{UNI}} = \sum_{i=1}^n \left[b \frac{\partial X_{ij}}{\partial A_{ij}} \frac{\partial A_{ij}}{\partial s_j^{UNI}} - A_{ij} (s_j^{UNI}) - s_j^{UNI} \frac{\partial A_{ij}}{\partial s_j^{UNI}} - \frac{\partial C_{ij}^g}{\partial A_{ij}} \frac{\partial A_{ij}}{\partial s_j^{UNI}} \right] = 0.$$

Equation (23) reflects that the regulator, when setting the uniform subsidy, takes into account the responses of all landholdings. Consequently, the optimal practice-based uniform subsidy s_j balances the marginal benefits of the subsidy, $\sum_{i=1}^n [b(\partial X_{ij}/\partial A_{ij}) \cdot (\partial A_{ij}/\partial s_j^{UNI})]$, with the marginal public expenditure cost of increasing the subsidy, $\sum_{i=1}^n [A_{ij}(s_j^{UNI}) + s_j(\partial A_{ij}/\partial s_j^{UNI}) + (\partial C_{ij}^g/\partial A_{ij}) \cdot (\partial A_{ij}/\partial s_j^{UNI})]$, where in the latter expression the first term, $\sum_{i=1}^n [A_{ij}(s_j^{UNI})]$ is the increased payment to already converted land, the second term $\sum_{i=1}^n [s_j^{UNI}(\partial A_{ij}/\partial s_j^{UNI})]$ is the increase in payments because of additionally enrolled land due to the increase in the subsidy, and the third term, $\sum_{i=1}^n [(\partial C_{ij}^g/\partial A_{ij}) \cdot (\partial A_{ij}/\partial s_j^{UNI})]$, is the increase in MRV costs due to the additionally enrolled area.

In the following sections, we apply this model empirically to compare the practice-based subsidy s_j^{UNI} that results from solving equation (23) numerically with the optimal results-based subsidy s_j^{OUT} defined in equation (14).

3. Data

This section describes the data used for applying the model. All economic data is in euro (€) and 2023-year value. When monetary values were originally available in Danish kroner, we first inflated to 2023 values using the Danish Consumer Price Index (CPI) from Statistics Denmark (2023a) and then convert to euro using average exchange rates from Denmark Nationalbank's StatBank (2023). When values were provided in euro, we inflate them using the average inflation rates for the euro area (Eurostat, 2024).

3.1. Landholding types

We classify all Danish farms into different landholding types, using data from Statistics Denmark (2023b). We use 75 representative landholding types, determined by location, size, and main production orientation. The location is one of the five regions in Denmark, Capital Region (*Hovedstaden*), Southern Denmark (*Syddanmark*), Zealand (*Sjælland*), Central Jutland (*Midtjylland*) and North Jutland (*Nordjylland*), together covering the whole country. The size is one of five categories: 0.1 to 19.9 hectares, 20 to 49.9 hectares, 50 to 124.9 hectares, 125 to 249.9 hectares, and 250 or more hectares, all of which are represented by the mean area in each category. The production orientation is one of three categories: pig, cattle, and plant. The number of farms from each landholding type is from Statistics Denmark (2023b). A table with all parameter values specific to farm types can be found in the Supplementary Material. We describe the data in the following sections.

3.2. Carbon sequestration

For all measures and landholdings, we parametrize the sequestration function $X_{ij}(A_{ij})$ as:

$$(24) \quad X_{ij}(A_{ij}) = x_{ij}A_{ij}.$$

where x_{ij} is a sequestration coefficient capturing the average yearly soil organic carbon (SOC) increase in tCO₂e/ha from implementing measure j in landholding i . The total sequestration provided by all measures implemented in the same hectares is assumed to be additive. The per hectare carbon sequestration for each farm is based on average rates from long-run simulations. For consistency, we report all sequestration outcomes in tCO₂e/ha/yr.

The per hectare carbon sequestration for cover cropping and grassland conversion in Denmark is obtained from Taghizadeh-Toosi and Olesen (2016). The authors report the average annual increase in SOC stocks profile (i.e. 0-100 cm layer) over 26 years for different soil types

(sand, sandy-loam, and loam) and for different production orientations, under typical management conditions⁹.

For reduced tillage, relevant experimental data from Denmark was not available for the full soil profile. Thus, we use the IPCC guidelines (IPCC 2019 p. 5.18) to calculate x_{ij} , estimating SOC changes in the top soil (0-30 cm) over a 20-year period comparing baseline management and reduced tillage. This choice reflects the IPCC Tier 1 assumption that management effects on SOC due to tillage occur within the topsoil layer (0–30 cm) While this differs from the depth coverage used for the other measures, it reflects the depth at which SOC responses to tillage are reported in the available empirical literature, and ensures the consistency of our model with standard greenhouse gas inventory reporting conventions.. Baseline SOC values are derived by multiplying the cropland area in the Danish region where the landholding is located (Statistics Denmark 2023c) with reference factors for temperate climates taken from the IPCC (2019) report for carbon stocks and land use and management input levels. For applying the formula, we assume medium input use as the baseline management, as defined by the IPCC (2019). This

⁹ In Taghizadeh-Toosi and Olesen (2016), sequestration effects are computed relative to ‘control farms’, i.e. typical Danish crop rotations without manure application, straw retention, or cover crops. Coefficients from two sampling sites in Denmark are reported, with the greatest possible temperature differences, the northernmost (57°33’19”N and 10° 20’13”E) and the southernmost (54°39’43”N and 11°28’50”E) part. The estimated sequestration responses are very similar across the two locations, while differences across soil types are substantially larger. Given the relatively small climatic gradient within Denmark and large soil type heterogeneity, we thus use the average of these to derive a single coefficient for each soil type in the country. These values are then matched to our farm production types and regions based on the regional soil types. We utilize a national topsoil map (Adhikari et al. 2013) and the soil classification system from Madsen et al. (1992) to determine the soil composition of each Danish region, computing a spatially weighted average for each farm type and region. Based on the data in Taghizadeh-Toosi and Olesen (2016), differentiation by production orientation is only possible for cover crops.

This estimate is also within the range of values presented by Eriksen et al. (2020), who calculates cover cropping costs under different cultivation practices and seed mixes in Denmark to be between 21–102 €/ha in 2023 year value. Dividing the r.h.s. of equation (25) by A_{ij} , we obtain the average cost of cover cropping as $\delta_{cc}A_{ij}$. Setting this equal to the above cost estimate and substituting A_{ij} for the average farm level area available for cover cropping, we obtain $\delta_{cc} = 6.6$.

For grassland conversion, we rely on results from an integrated EU-wide agricultural sector model, CAPRI (Gocht et al. 2016). Gocht et al. show that a 5% increase in grassland area across all NUTS regions,¹³ i.e. the conversion of 2.9 million hectares of land, can be achieved at a total cost of 527.51 € million in 2023-year value. Assuming that the average cost would apply in Denmark and substituting A_{ij} for the average farm-level area deemed available for grassland conversion, we obtain $\delta_{grass} = 42.5$.¹⁴

Finally, for reduced tillage, studies suggest potential cost savings from reduced machinery, fuel and labor (European Commission 2023; Laage-Thomsen and Jacobsen 2024; Munkholm et al. 2020; Troccoli et al. 2015). Simultaneously, there can be yield losses and/or increased costs from application of fertilizers and plant protection products to maintain agricultural output (European Commission 2023; Laage-Thomsen and Jacobsen 2024; Laukkanen and Nauges 2011). Laage-Thomsen and Jacobsen (2024), using data from the European Commission (2023), estimate mitigation costs for reduced tillage to be between 120-827 DKK/ha in Denmark (corresponding to 16 and 110 €/ha in 2023 year value). We use the lower cost out of the two values for deriving the mitigation cost parameter used in our model, as a

¹³ NUTS regions are classified under the Nomenclature of Territorial Units for Statistics (NUTS).

¹⁴ There is to our knowledge no corresponding cost estimates for Denmark specifically. Opportunity costs may differ between countries, but we believe this estimate serves as a reasonable proxy for land-use trade-offs in Denmark.

conservative average cost estimate that allows the model to reach higher per hectare costs at full implementation. Setting A_{ij} equal to the average area deemed available for reduced tillage, we obtain $\delta_{till} = 0.48$.

3.5. Private transaction costs

We parametrize transaction costs as a convex, quadratic function of total sequestration (and thus implicitly as dependent on the area of implementation), assuming that these costs increase with scale due to rising administrative and coordination burdens. While the shape of the transaction cost function is *à priori* indeterminate (Stavins 1999), empirical meta-studies such as Phan et al. (2017) and Karpavicius et al. (2026) find no evidence of economies of scale. Further, to the best of our knowledge, there are no empirical studies showing economies of scale in transactions for environmental economic applications broadly.

Equation (26) reports our assumed transaction cost function, where $\beta_j > 0$ is a scaling factor.

$$(26) \quad C_{ij}^t(X_{ij}) = \beta_j(X_{ij})^2.$$

Solving equation (26) for β_j we get:

$$(27) \quad \beta_j = \frac{C_{ij}^t(X_{ij})}{(X_{ij})^2}.$$

Substituting X_{ij} by the corresponding formula in equation (24), equation (27) can be rewritten as:

$$(28) \quad \beta_j = \frac{C_{ij}^t(X_{ij})}{A_{ij}} \frac{1}{(x_{ij})^2 A_{ij}}.$$

To estimate the values of β_j , we use the data from Bamière et al. (2014), which reports the average private transaction costs per hectare (i.e., $C_{ij}^t(X_{ij})/A_{ij}$) for different sequestration measures in France. In their study, private transaction costs are defined as farmers' time and effort devoted to searching for information, negotiating and renegotiating contractual

arrangements, and completing administrative tasks associated with practice adoption. The authors apply a transaction cost function originally estimated within the ITAES FP6 project and transfer this function to French agriculture using microdata from the French Farm Accountancy Data Network (FADN/RICA) for 2010. For each mitigation action, Bamière et al. (2014) compute a national average transaction cost. We use these values, reported in their Table 4, by choosing practices closest to the measures considered in this study. For grassland conversion, specifically, we use Bamière et al.'s (2014) estimate for grassland management.. This choice is motivated by the fact that transaction costs associated with grassland conversion arise from the adoption and management of grassland practices, while the sequestration benefits of conversion also depend on how grassland is subsequently managed. We adjust the per hectare transaction cost values reported by Bamière et al. (2014) to reflect the Danish context by applying a conversion factor of 1.4, corresponding to the ratio between the per capita GDP of Denmark and France in 2010 (World Bank, 2010). The resulting per hectare transaction costs are then 22.7 €/ha for cover cropping, 24.22 €/ha for reduced tillage, and 32.35 €/ha for grassland conversion in 2023 year-value. This estimates are within the same order of magnitude as the average transaction costs estimated for European (Mettepenningen et al. 2009) and German farmers (Weber 2014), as well as commonly assumed values for farm-level transaction costs in Danish assessments of agri-environmental schemes, ranging between 13 and 66 €/ha (see, e.g., Jacobsen 2015; Olsen 2016; Pedersen 2020, 2024; Pedersen and Jacobsen, 2019). The choice to use data from Bamière et al.'s study is motivated by per hectare transaction costs being differentiated across sequestration measures and estimates being empirically grounded from farm-level accounting data. We substitute the remaining terms in the equation by the average found in our data, i.e., we substitute A_{ij} for the average area deemed available for carbon sequestration for each measure and x_{ij} by the average per hectare sequestration for each measure. The resulting values for β_j are $\beta_{cc} = 154$, $\beta_{grass} = 0.9$, $\beta_{till} = 18.4$.

3.6. Average total per hectare adoption costs

Based on the above, the average adoption costs, including both mitigation and transaction costs, will approximately be 107 €/ha for cover cropping, 214 €/ha for grassland conversion and 40 €/ha for reduced tillage. These estimates can be checked for relevancy against average willingness to accept (WTA) sequestration contracts (all converted to 2023 prices). Hasler et al. (2019a) finds an average WTA of ~276 €/ha for cover crop contracts in Denmark. Zandersen et al. (2016) suggests between 27 and 130 €/ha are needed for farmers to engage in reduced tillage. To our knowledge, no studies have directly assessed WTA for grassland conversion in Denmark. Thus, our total average per hectare adoption cost estimates appear to be conservative when compared to estimates from stated preference studies.

3.7. Public transaction costs

Direct inspections to check compliance with agri-environmental schemes in Denmark are carried out according to EU-regulations (Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries in Denmark 2024). In line with these regulations, we assume that compliance with a practice-based scheme will imply a periodical audit observing the management practices on the contracted area. For the results-based subsidy, we assume that compliance additionally will cover the measurement of SOC, following the approach in Antle et al. (2003). We consider the measurement would be done with periodical samples checking the SOC accumulation associated with an adopted measure. For the frequency of monitoring, we apply the mandatory soil monitoring obligations under the proposed common EU framework for soil health assessment and reporting, which recommends a 5 year monitoring frequency (European Commission 2023). This is also in line with the typical length of EU agri-environmental contracts (European Commission 2015). Additionally, we assume that all contracted hectares are checked during an audit. This differs from the requirements in Article 32 of the EU Control

Regulation 809/2014 that suggests annual on-the-spot checks for only a minimum of 5% of beneficiaries with recurring agri-environmental commitments (European Commission 2014). However, our assumption of complete monitoring can be justified given that limited monitoring can exacerbate moral hazard in agri-environmental schemes, particularly when penalties for noncompliance are weak (Hart and Latacz-Lohmann 2005). By assuming all contracted hectares would be checked during the contract period, we disregard farmers' strategic behavior and focus on a setting where compliance is enforced perfectly. In sensitivity analysis, we test for different monitoring frequencies.

For parametrizing $C_{ij}^g(A_{ij})$, we adopt a bottom-up approach, considering the costs of different MRV activities. The MRV cost function is described as:

$$(29) \quad C_{ij}^g(A_{ij}) = (Transport_i + Operation + Preparation + Lab) \cdot A_{ij} \cdot 0.2$$

In equation (29), $Transport_i$ are the average fuel and time costs for transportation to and from the farm for the audit, assumed to vary across landholdings based on location. $Operation$ are labor costs for inspecting during the audit. These two costs apply for both subsidies. Finally, $Preparation$ are the costs for preparing sample plots (i.e., handling, labeling, and packaging and other activities related with taking soil samples in the field and preparing them for laboratory analysis) and Lab are the laboratorial costs for analyzing the samples. These two costs apply exclusively to the results-based scheme. Consequently, MRV costs will depend on policy design, with practice-based schemes incurring lower costs by construction. We assume that per hectare operation, laboratory, and preparation costs are uniform across the landholdings. Finally, because we assume a 5-year monitoring frequency, the parameters are multiplied by an adjustment factor of 0.2. All cost parameters from the expression are in €/ha.

We assume that MRV activities in Denmark would be carried out by the Danish Agricultural Agency, which is the institution responsible for the administration of agri-

environmental support and for inspections to verify that conditions for grants are met (Ministry of Food, Agriculture and Fisheries in Denmark 2024). The agency has multiple regional offices. Based thereon, we assume one monitoring center exists in each region. To calculate the transportation time of the monitoring agents, we first estimate the average time driving from the center point of a region to a random point in the same region, assuming each region is a circle with radius R .¹⁵ We use the regional centroid as a simplifying assumption to represent a monitoring center placed to minimize average travel distances within the region provided that farms are uniformly distributed. Taking into account the return trip, an average driving speed of 80 km/h, salary levels for the agents in the car, and fuel costs, we calculate $Transport_i$ assuming full implementation of measures and that a maximum of two neighboring farms can be visited per day, with no added driving distance between them. With this procedure, although transport costs apply to both subsidy designs, they affect total MRV expenditure differently because the model yields different spatial optimal adoption patterns under practice- versus results-based schemes. To calculate operation, preparation, and laboratory costs we follow the approach by Mäkipää et al. (2008). The authors calculate the costs of monitoring carbon stocks and changes in Finnish forests by estimating the time required and the number of people necessary for different MRV activities and use salary rates to determine the associated monetary costs. For our case, we assume the same time and personnel requirements as Mäkipää et al. (2008), based on the hypothesis that field-based carbon monitoring in agriculture involves similar requirements as in forested landscapes, due to the need for trained personnel in both contexts and a similar nature of on-site measurement protocols. We adapt the calculations in Mäkipää et al. (2008) by using Danish salary levels for relevant professionals obtained from Statistics Denmark (2022). For all activities, including transportation, we assume two

¹⁵ The average distance in km from a regional monitoring center to a farm located within the region is thus $2R/3$.

monitoring agents will be required, as hypothesized by Mäkipää et al. (2008). Details can be found in Table A.1 in Appendix A.

In the above-described parametrization of MRV costs, it is implicitly assumed that monitoring is performed separately for each measure. This could lead to an overestimation of the MRV costs. However, calibrating the parameters under the assumption of full implementation implies a tendency to underestimate MRV costs because transport costs are distributed across the largest possible number of hectares. Taken together, our estimates could be reasonably balanced.

With this parametrization, total average annual practice- and results- based MRV costs over all areas deemed available for sequestration equal 53.8 and 128 €/ha, respectively. Thus, MRV costs are assumed to be, on average, 2.4 higher for the results-based subsidy relative to the practice-based one. MRV costs for the practice-based subsidy then make up between 20 and 57% of the total costs of the subsidy (i.e. the sum of adoption costs, see section 3.6, and MRV costs) and between 37 and 76% for results-based instruments.

4. Results

The model was solved using non-linear programming (NLP) in the software GAMS (GAMS Development Corporation, 2023) with a CONOPT4 solver. First, we estimate the maximum net benefits associated with the first-best allocation of sequestration measures by running the model described in equation (5) and including MRV costs for a results-based scheme, deriving the Pigouvian subsidy to sequestration output. Next, we run the model described in equation (16), including MRV costs for a practice-based scheme and thus deriving the second-best uniform subsidy s_j^{UNI} for each measure.

We simulate the models for a value of b between 50 and 1,000 € per tCO₂e. The lower end of this range is similar to carbon prices found under the EU Emissions Trading Scheme (EU

ETS), which generally trades between 60 and 100 €/tCO_{2e} (European Commission 2024b; OECD 2022a), and the recently introduced Danish carbon tax on agriculture, expected to reach approximately 40 €/ tCO_{2e} by 2035 (DR 2024). Higher levels for the Danish agricultural tax were initially suggested by, e.g., the Danish Climate Council (2023) which recommended a carbon tax of 200-220 €/tCO_{2e}. The upper limit of 1,000 €/tCO_{2e} goes beyond current policy recommendations to reflect the uncertainty in future market dynamics and climate scenarios. The limit of 1,000 €/tCO_{2e} is similar to levels from probabilistic price trajectory estimations by Rogelj et al. (2013) required to limit global average temperature increases to 2°C by 2095, and probabilistic price projections under a 1.5°C target by 2100 by Marcucci et al. (2019). Equally high carbon price values have been used parameters in other research applied in the land use sector, e.g. Humpenöder et al. (2014). The inclusion of a broad range of carbon prices in our modelling enables a systematic assessment of the robustness of outcomes under varying market and policy settings.

4.1. Subsidy outcomes: Net benefits and carbon sequestration

Figure 1 presents the total net benefits (*NB*) in €, across carbon price levels. For both subsidies, the net benefits increase with rising carbon prices, as expected. The figure shows that, under both schemes, a carbon price of 50€/tCO_{2e} is sufficient to incentivize carbon sequestration. Notably, the results-based subsidy results in between 1.4 and 1.6 times higher total net benefits across all carbon prices relative to the practice-based subsidy. This suggests that the cost savings from directing sequestration efforts to landholdings and measures with higher sequestration compensate for the higher MRV costs of the results-based scheme.

Figure 2 illustrates total carbon sequestration achieved (in 1,000 tCO_{2e}). The results-based subsidy yields between 47 to 66% more sequestration relative to the practice-based subsidy for a given carbon price.

4.3. Composition of total costs of subsidies

Figure 5 brings the share of each cost component in total costs of implementing the subsidies, i.e. private transaction, mitigation, MRV costs, and the farmer's rent under the practice-based subsidy (equal to $s_j^{UNI} * A_{ij} - C_{ij}^m - C_{ij}^t$), for three carbon prices: 250 €/tCO_{2e}, 500 €/tCO_{2e} and 1,000 €/tCO_{2e}. As noted in the figure, the rent represents 50-59% of the total costs for the practice-based subsidy, illustrating the high payments above farmer's actual costs of adoption. In contrast, the results-based subsidy's cost composition is primarily driven by mitigation and MRV costs. At a carbon price equal to 250 €/tCO_{2e}, MRV costs represent 28% of the costs for the results-based subsidy and 16% for the practice-based subsidy. As carbon prices increase, the share of MRV costs decreases in relation to the total costs for both subsidies. That is because at higher carbon prices, more landholdings with high adoption costs for carbon sequestration have a positive area allocation. This, along with quadratic adoption cost functions, causes total transaction and mitigation costs to increase more than the increase in MRV costs.

4.4. Sensitivity analysis

To test the robustness of our findings, we conduct sensitivity analyses where assumed parameters are varied by 10% one at a time. Results are available in Table A.2 in the Appendix. We check the sensitivity in terms of the impact on net benefits of results- and practice-based subsidies, and on the ratio of the two (with the results-based subsidy in the nominator), across three carbon prices: 250 €/tCO_{2e}, 500 €/tCO_{2e} and 1,000 €/tCO_{2e}. We check the impact of assumptions about transport costs, private transaction costs, mitigation costs, areas available for cover cropping, grassland conversion and reduced tillage, as well as a different monitoring frequency, against the baseline assumption of a 5-year monitoring frequency. The impact on net benefits ratio is less than 2% across all parameters, suggesting results are relatively robust.

These findings agree with previous literature that results-based approaches are more cost-effective than uniform payments (see e.g., Antle et al. 2003; Parks and Hardie 1995; Pautsch et al. 2001). Previous authors have disregarded the role of public and private transaction costs (Parks and Hardie 1995; Pautsch et al. 2001) or optimized payment values without accounting for the MRV costs (Antle et al. 2003), focusing only on the mitigation costs of measures. We show that accounting for public transaction costs will not alter the preference for results-based instruments as long as MRV costs per hectare for measuring sequestration do not exceed the MRV costs for practice-based schemes by factors of 3.5 to 8 at carbon prices of 250 and 1,000 €/tCO₂e, respectively.

Our paper has limitations. First, due to limited data availability, we assume that private transaction and mitigation costs are similar across the two subsidies, where in practice they may depend on the policy design. The models' static nature additionally does not account for the fact that subsidies may alter landholdings' specialization. For example, payments for grasslands could increase the number of livestock farms in Denmark. Institutional conditions in the land market may also affect scheme uptake but are not captured in our model. In Denmark, where a considerable share of agricultural land is rented, tenants may have limited ability to adopt measures involving more permanent changes if these require landowner consent or long-term commitments. In addition, area-based support may be capitalized into higher land prices or rents, so that part of the subsidy accrues to landowners rather than the farmer, which may make participation less attractive over time. Our model is also limited to changes in soil organic carbon. We do not account for changes in biomass carbon stocks or other greenhouse gas emissions, which are beyond the scope of this analysis but may affect the net climate impact of the measures considered. Finally, we assume only adoption costs determine farmer's choices to participate in schemes. In reality, there is evidence that risk-averse farmers may prefer predictable, practice-based payments (OECD 2022b) and that risk-

aversion and the severity of punishment for non-compliance can influence voluntary adoption of measures (Hart and Latacz-Lohmann 2005). In addition, participation in agri-environmental schemes is found to be affected by other behavioral factors, such as network or peer effects, and attitudes towards agri-environmental schemes or other policies (Schaub et al. 2023). For example, differentiated payments may be perceived as unfair and encounter challenges for farm uptake. We thus suggest future research may strive to incorporate behavioral heterogeneity on preferences, where farm level data exists. Relevant behavioral data includes, e.g., farmers' responses to payment contract attributes including not only orientation (i.e. action or practice-based) but also duration, flexibility, type of monitoring, and whether or not technical and administrative support is provided within the specific contract context.

Despite the limitations, the findings from this study have implications for agri-environmental policy. Within the Danish carbon sequestration context, we bring evidence that policymakers should invest in reducing MRV costs to support the implementation of results-based schemes that promote higher carbon sequestration in agriculture. The modeling framework used in this paper can be adapted using data from primary (or experimental) data collection, thus offering a supporting tool for *ex ante* policy evaluation that may support the agricultural sector's transition toward more climate-friendly production systems while maintaining viable income for farmers.

Acknowledgements

We are grateful for helpful comments from Mark Brady and Brian H. Jacobsen on an earlier version of the manuscript. We are also grateful for the editor and two anonymous reviewers whose comments greatly improved this study. This work was funded by the Independent Research Fund Denmark [grant # 0217-00124B] and the EU Horizon projects MARVIC [grant # 101112942] and INTERCEDE [grant # 101135159].

Conflict of interest statement

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

Data availability statement

All data used in this study are available in the Appendix and as supplementary material. Details regarding data selection and calibration are provided within the manuscript. Code used for reproducibility (implemented in GAMs) will be made openly available on GitHub at <https://github.com/lkarpavicius/Practice--vs-results-based-subsidies> upon the paper publication.

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